

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

The Influence of workload, work stress, work motivation and organizational commitment on nurse performance in the intensive room at Bahteramas Regional Hospital, Southeast Sulawesi Province in 2023

I Nengah Sunarto *, Yusuf Sabilu and Nani Yuniar

Department of Public Health, Public Health Faculty, Halu Oleo University, Kendari, Indonesia.

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Abstract

Introduction: In facing increasingly heavy work demands in intensive care units, nurses often experience high workloads. Excessive workload can potentially cause a decrease in nurse performance and increase the risk of errors as well as impact on organizational commitment. The aim of the research is to analyze the influence of workload, work stress, work motivation and organizational commitment on the performance of nurses in the intensive care unit at Bahteramas Hospital, Southeast Sulawesi Province in 2023.

Method: This type of research is quantitative research using an observational analytical design with a cross sectional approach. The research sample consisted of 64 people. The research instrument used a questionnaire and data was analyzed using the chi-square test.

Results: The results showed that there was a significant influence of workload on nurse performance ($p=0.000$), there was a significant influence of work stress on nurse performance ($p=0.000$), there was an influence of work motivation on nurse performance ($p=0.000$) and there was an influence of organizational commitment on Nurse performance ($p=0.003$) in the intensive care unit at Bahteramas Regional Hospital, Southeast Sulawesi Province.

Conclusion: There is an influence of work load, work stress, work motivation, and work commitment on the performance of nurses in the intensive care unit at Bahteramas Regional Hospital, Southeast Sulawesi Province in 2023. It is recommended that the hospital management provide positive support in order to reduce the level of work stress of nurses so as to increase work enthusiasm and evaluation. towards nurses' work motivation, such as providing a fair opportunity for each nurse to develop their career and providing rewards for good nurse performance.

Keywords: Workload; Job Stress; Work motivation; Organizational Commitment; Nurse Performance

1. Introduction

Today's health system is faced with increasingly complex and dynamic challenges, especially in intensive care units, where nurses have a critical role in providing quality care to patients who require intensive attention. The performance of nurses in the intensive care unit greatly influences patient care outcomes and the success of the health system as a whole. In the world of healthcare, the intensive care unit is considered a stressful work environment and requires a high level of expertise. Intensive care nurses are responsible for the care of critical patients, and are expected to work in fast-paced, dynamic conditions, and often face emergency situations. In this context, nurse performance is a key factor that influences patient care outcomes and hospital operational success. Intensive spaces in health care delivery require rapid response, effective team coordination, and high adaptability from nurses. In this context, the role of the nurse not only

* Corresponding author: I Nengah Sunarto

involves complex technical tasks, but also requires the ability to manage a high workload and the potential stress that arises[1].

In facing increasingly heavy work demands in intensive care units, nurses often experience high workloads. Excessive workload can potentially cause a decrease in nurse performance and increase the risk of errors in providing care². Apart from that, work stress is also a factor that can affect psychological and physical well-being, and has the potential to reduce nurse performance. The increased workload of nurses, especially in intensive care settings, can create major challenges that can affect physical and mental well-being[3]. Coupled with work stress that may arise from critical situations and high task demands, nurses are often faced with pressure that can have a negative impact on nurse performance. On the other hand, work motivation can be an important driver that influences how nurses respond to workload and stress, thereby potentially improving or worsening nurse performance.

Several factors can influence the performance of nurses, namely the high workload and complexity of nursing responsibilities which will increasingly burden nurses and can cause complaints of pain, fatigue and unexpected emotions [4]. High workloads can negatively impact nurses' ability to provide quality care. Along with that, work stress is also an important aspect that plays a role in the psychological condition of nurses. Constant stress can result in decreased motivation and mental well-being, which in turn can affect nurse performance. Nurses working in critical care areas have a higher level of stressors because the clients in the area are very complex, nurses must be skilled, and they are also required for continuous observation [5] .

A high level of motivation can improve nurse performance by encouraging them to overcome obstacles and remain focused on nursing tasks. Work motivation, as an internal factor that encourages individuals to achieve goals and improve the quality of work, can be a key factor in improving the performance of nurses in intensive care. High motivation can help nurses overcome workload and work stress, thus having a positive impact on nurse performance. Therefore, workload, work stress, and work motivation are necessities that will support the performance of nurses in the intensive care unit[6].

Organizational commitment to the performance of nurses in intensive care is an important focus in the context of quality health services. Some opinions related to organizational commitment are the identification of strengths related to the values and goals of maintaining membership in the Hospital[7]. Efforts to improve nurse performance through the application of maximum nursing care, human resources are very influential, especially in the level of nurse competency, motivation to work and also the workload they bear. Research conducted by Budiawan (2015), the results of his research concluded that nurse performance is influenced by the competency of nurses, work motivation and workload.[8].

Based on an initial survey conducted at the Bahteramas Regional General Hospital, Southeast Sulawesi Province, information was obtained that the number of nurses working was 244 people, specifically 63 nurses working in the intensive care room. (Bahteramas Regional Hospital, 2023). Then, based on the results of interviews via questionnaires from 30 intensive care nurses, data was obtained as to 11 (36.7%) nurses who had high performance, and 19 (63.3)% of nurses who had low performance. The average number of nurses on duty per shift is 3 nurses to care for 38 patients, which shows the high workload of nurses. These data show that the workload of nurses is very large and the demand for improving nurse performance is urgently needed. To improve the competency of nurses in carrying out their duties serving patients, Bahteramas Regional Hospital, Southeast Sulawesi Province has sent several nurses out of town for training or comparative studies.

The selection of an intensive room as a research location is based on strategic considerations. The intensive care unit is a particularly relevant environment for exploring these factors, because the crucial role of nurses in providing intensive care gives rise to high levels of workload and the potential for significant stress. This research is considered important to explore the impact of complex workloads, levels of stress that may arise, and work motivation on nurses' performance, with the hope of providing in-depth insight regarding efforts to improve working conditions and increase the quality of service in intensive care units. Thus, the selection of the intensive care unit as the site of this study not only ensures the relevance of the findings to a practical context, but can also make a meaningful contribution to nurses' understanding of the dynamics of these factors in this critical health care environment.

Based on the background description above, researchers are interested in conducting research with the title "The Influence of Work Load, Work Stress, Work Motivation and Organizational Commitment on the performance of nurses in the intensive care unit at Bahteramas Hospital, Southeast Sulawesi Province in 2023".

2. Method

This research adopted a quantitative method using an observational analytical design with a cross sectional approach. The research was carried out at the Bahteramas Regional General Hospital from February to March 2024. Data was collected through filling out questionnaires. The sample consisted of 64 respondents selected using the total sampling method which were divided into two groups: group. Data were analyzed using the chi-square test.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Respondent Characteristics

Based on data from table 1, it can be seen that the characteristics of respondents based on age in the intensive care unit at Bahteramas Regional Hospital are dominated by the 31-39 year age group, with the number reaching 30 people (46.8%). From the characteristics of respondents based on gender, it was dominated by women, reaching 52 people (81.3%), in terms of recent education, the majority of respondents in the intensive care unit at Bahteramas Regional Hospital had a nursing background with a total of 37 people (57.8%).

Table 1 Distribution of Respondents Based on Respondent Characteristics in Bahteramas Regional Hospital, Prov. Southeast Sulawesi in 2023

No	Respondent Characteristics		Number (n)	Percentage(%)	Total
1.	Age	22-30 years old	17	26.6	64
		31-39 years old	30	46.8	
		40-48 years old	14	21.8	
		49-57 years old	3	4.7	
2.	Gender	Man	12	18.7	64
		Woman	52	81.3	
3	Last education	D3 Nursing	19	29.7	64
		Bachelor's Degree in Nursing	8	12.5	
		Nurse	37	57.8	

Source: Primary Data, 2023

3.2 Bivariate Analysis

Table 2 The Influence of Workload on the Performance of Intensive Room Nurses at Bahteramas Regional Hospital, Southeast Sulawesi Province

Workload	Nurse Performance				Total		P-value
	Tall		Low		N	%	
	n	%	n	%			
Tall	6	13.3	39	86.7	45	100	0.000
Low	14	73.7	5	26.3	19	100	
Total	20	31.2	44	68.8	64	100	

Source: Primary Data, 2023

Based on the results from table 2, it was found that there was an influence of workload on the performance of intensive care nurses at Bahteramas Regional Hospital, Southeast Sulawesi Province in 2023, with a p-value of 0.000, which indicates that $p < 0.05$.

It is known that 39 respondents (86.7%) had a high workload resulting in low nurse performance. Based on the results of interviews and filling out questionnaires conducted by researchers, respondents provided information that the work given to nurses exceeded the actual portion, thus making nurses feel overwhelmed in serving patients, nurses had to work as quickly as possible and felt like they were racing against time, there was a lack of nursing staff in the room compared to clients, every time a nurse is faced with the right decision, there is a responsibility to carry out client care which is the hope of hospital leadership for quality services.

This research is in line with research conducted by Hakman et al (2017), showing that there is a significant influence between the workload experienced by nurses and the performance of nurses for Covid-19 patients at the Kendari City Regional Hospital so that the hypothesis carried out can be accepted[9]. Another research conducted by Wicaksana (2015), stated that workload had a positive and significant influence on the performance of nurses at the Yogyakarta PDHI Islamic Hospital[10].

These findings indicate that workload is a crucial factor in maintaining the quality of nursing services, and emphasize the importance of effective workload management strategies in supporting improved nurse performance in the health environment. This study aims to explore the relationship between the workload experienced by nurses and nurse performance in the context of nursing services. In the dynamic and often demanding world of health care, it is important to understand how the level of nursing workload can impact a nurse's ability to provide quality care to patients.

Table 3 The Effect of Work Stress on the Performance of Intensive Room Nurses at Bahteramas Regional Hospital, Southeast Sulawesi Province in 2023

Work stress	Nurse Performance				Total		P-value
	Tall		Low		N	%	
	n	%	n	%			
Tall	5	12.5	35	87.5	40	100	0.000
Low	12	62.5	9	37.5	24	100	
Total	20	31.2	44	68.8	64	100	

Source: Primary Data, 2023

Based on the results from table 3, it was found that there was an influence of work stress on the performance of intensive care nurses at Bahteramas Regional Hospital, Southeast Sulawesi Province in 2023, with a p-value of 0.000, which indicates that $p < 0.05$.

The results of the study showed that some respondents or 87.5% had high work stress resulting in low nurse performance. Data obtained based on the results of interviews and filling out questionnaires provides information that nurses experience tiredness after caring for or dealing with patients in critical conditions, feel that there are many additional tasks that interfere with my role as a nurse, lack concentration and easily forget when working, have difficulty managing rest time because too much work, feeling stiff neck, shoulder or back muscles when/after working in the hospital. This is also because respondents are not motivated to do their work well or do not feel satisfied with their work, which can cause low performance, respondents have limitations in the skills or knowledge needed to do their work effectively, thus causing low performance, and respondents being placed in roles or tasks that do not suit their skills or interests, which can reduce their motivation and performance.

This research is in line with previous research conducted by Friska Aprilia (2017), the results of her research stated that work stress had a significant effect on the performance of nurses at Ibnu Sina Islamic Hospital Pekanbaru [11]. The results of this research are also supported by previous research conducted by Alpira Febrianti (2021), stating that there is a relationship between the level of work stress and the performance of nurses at Labuang Baji Regional Hospital [12].

Based on the results from table 4, it was found that there is an influence of work motivation on the performance of intensive care nurses at Bahteramas Regional Hospital, Southeast Sulawesi Province in 2023, with a p-value of 0.000, which indicates that $p < 0.05$.

Table 4. The Influence of Work Motivation on the Performance of Intensive Room Nurses at Bahteramas Regional Hospital, Southeast Sulawesi Province in 2023

Work motivation	Nurse Performance				Total		P-value
	Tall		Low		N	%	
	n	%	n	%			
Tall	14	60.9	9	39.1	23	100	0.000
Low	6	14.6	35	85.4	41	100	
Total	20	31.2	44	68.8	64	100	

Source: Primary Data, 2023

It is known that only 35 respondents (85.4%) had low work motivation and low nurse performance. The results of interviews and filling out questionnaires conducted by researchers on respondents provide information that nurses are required to be motivated by their work as nurses and have the confidence to be able to carry out their duties well and the need to save patients' lives is one of the motives for nurses to be willing to work wholeheartedly. Apart from that, because of the support of unified colleagues who provide motivation to fellow nurses who work in the intensive care unit. Feel challenged when facing difficulties in completing assignments because there is a human side to fight for.

This study also found that low levels of work motivation were significantly associated with low nurse performance. Nurses who have strong motivation tend to demonstrate better compliance with procedures, quicker responses to patient needs, and more effective collaboration with the medical team. However, work motivation is not just the passion that burns within a person. External factors, such as support from management, a positive work environment, and career development opportunities, also play an important role in fostering sustained motivation. With the right support and stimulation, nurses' work motivation can provide high quality health service results.

The results of this research are in line with the research results of Friska Aprilia (2021), stating that the better the work motivation felt by nurses, the better the nurse's performance will be [11]. Likewise, the results of research conducted by Hakman et al (2017) stated that high work motivation will tend to produce good nurse performance. [9]. The results of this conclusion are also in line with the results of research by Ritonga (2010), showing that there is a significant influence between work motivation on the performance of nurses at RSU Imelda Medan [13].

Table 5 The Influence of Organizational Commitment on the Performance of Intensive Room Nurses at Bahteramas Regional Hospital, Southeast Sulawesi Province in 2023

Organizational Commitment	Nurse Performance				Total		P-value
	Tall		Low		n	%	
	n	%	n	%			
Tall	3	11.1	24	88.9	27	100	0.003
Low	17	45.9	20	54.1	37	100	
Total	20	31.2	44	68.8	64	100	

Source: Primary Data, 2023

Based on the results from table 5, it was found that there was an influence of organizational commitment on the performance of intensive care nurses at Bahteramas Hospital, Southeast Sulawesi Province in 2023, with a p-value of 0.003, which indicates that $p < 0.05$.

This is supported by research data obtained during the research where the majority or 20 respondents (54.1%) had low organizational commitment which also resulted in low nurse performance. Information from the results of filling out questionnaires carried out on respondents shows that the majority of respondents find it very difficult to agree with organizational policies regarding important matters relating to nursing staff. Nurses also receive almost all types of work assignments in order to continue working in the organization where they work.

The results of interviews in this study revealed that nurses who have a high level of organizational commitment tend to show better performance. Nurses demonstrated higher levels of compliance with procedures, quicker responses to patient needs, and better collaboration within the medical team. This research is in line with research conducted by Wicaksana (2015), stating that organizational commitment has a positive and significant influence on the performance of nurses at the Yogyakarta PDHI Islamic Hospital[10].

The results of this research can also be influenced by several factors including length of service, age and education. It was found that nurses with longer tenure tend to have higher levels of organizational commitment, while younger nurses may show lower levels of commitment but may increase with work experience. Additionally, nurses with higher levels of education tend to have higher levels of organizational commitment because they may feel more connected to their profession and have greater motivation to contribute to the growth of the organization.

3.3 Multivariate Analysis

Table 6 Multivariate analysis of independent variables on the performance of intensive care nurses at Bahteramas Regional Hospital, Southeast Sulawesi Province in 2023

		B	Sig.	Exp(B)	95.0% CI for Exp(B)	
					Lower	Upper
Step 2 ^a	Workload	-3.649	0.001	0.033	0.003	0.324
	Work stress	-3.573	0.002	0.028	0.003	0.287
	Work motivation	1.001	0.975	2.722	0.403	18,388
	Organizational commitment	-2.045	0.046	0.209	0.024	1.836
	Constant	14.609	0.000	2.212E6		
	R2 = 69.8 %					

Source: Primary Data, 2023

Based on the results from table 6, it shows that the variables that have the most influence on the performance of intensive care nurses are workload with a value of $\text{Exp}(B) = 0.033$, work stress with a value of $\text{Exp}(B) = 0.028$, work motivation with a value of $\text{Exp}(B) = 2.722$, and organizational commitment with a value of $\text{Exp}(B) = 0.209$. Meanwhile, in step 2a, work motivation is not included as a variable that has the most influence on the performance of intensive care nurses. The R Square (R^2) value was 0.698 or equal to 69.8%, this shows that workload, work stress and organizational commitment simultaneously or together have an effect of 69.8% on the performance of intensive care nurses. The remaining 30.2% (100%-69.8%) is influenced by other factors outside this regression equation or variables not examined in this research. Meanwhile, work motivation is considered not to simultaneously or jointly influence the performance of intensive care nurses.

Thus, workload, work stress and organizational commitment influence the performance of intensive care nurses at Bahteramas Regional Hospital, Southeast Sulawesi Province in 2023.

The research results show that the majority of respondents have a high workload, resulting in low performance. Most respondents' workload was measured through various factors, including the number of patients handled, case complexity, and administrative demands, while nurse performance was evaluated through indicators such as compliance with procedures, response to patient needs, and level of patient satisfaction. Most respondents experienced decreased compliance with procedures, increased levels of fatigue, and less rapid response to patient needs. Most respondents should be able to handle a variety of cases, from simple to complex, while maintaining focus and caution. However, as workloads increase, nurses often find themselves caught in demanding situations.

The results of this research are in line with the results of Ahmad Hannani's research (2016), stating that workload has a positive and significant effect on the performance of nurses in the Mawar Care Room, Floor II, RSUD Makassar. By understanding the importance of workload in influencing nurse performance, steps can be taken to manage workload effectively. This can involve a more equitable distribution of tasks, improving support systems, training in stress management, and promoting overall employee well-being. By reducing excessive workload and creating a supportive work environment, healthcare organizations can improve nurse performance, improve the patient experience, and ensure the continuation of quality healthcare services[14].

Nurses' workload consists not only of the number of patients handled, but also the complexity of cases, the severity of conditions, and the ever-increasing demands of administrative tasks. Nurses must face constant physical and mental stress to provide quality care, while maintaining a high level of care. Employee workload needs to be paid attention to so that there is no overload which can cause stress and can result in a decrease in employee work[15]

4. Conclusion

There is an influence of work load, work stress, work motivation, and work commitment on the performance of nurses in the intensive care unit at Bahteramas Regional Hospital, Southeast Sulawesi Province in 2023. The suggestion in this research is the need to pay attention to the workload imposed on employees by carrying out regular workload analysis as written in Minister of Home Affairs Regulation No. 12 of 2008. Hospitals must be able to minimize the work stress experienced by nurses by paying more attention on aspects that can influence the emergence of work stress. In particular, the hospital must be able to maintain relationships between its employees, so that work conflicts do not occur, reduce excessive workload for employees, especially those who are not their responsibility, and it is necessary to evaluate the work motivation of nurses, such as giving each nurse a fair opportunity to develop their career, providing rewards for good nurse performance, and equal opportunities for promotion.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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